

PEDAGOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF SOCIALY ACTIVE PERSONALITY QUALITIES IN GIRLS

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Annotation:

This article analyzes such directions as the development of healthy and harmonious development of girls in our country, the realization of their creative and intellectual potential, pedagogical aspects of the formation of socially active personality qualities, the development of legislation in their social protection.

Keywords and phrases: primary school, family and school, socially active person, primary school teacher, student girls, pedagogical process, positive qualities.

INTRODUCTION

In our republic, all necessary conditions and opportunities are being created for girls to be healthy and well-rounded, to realize their creative and intellectual potential, to fully meet the requirements of the 21st century, and to grow up as mature individuals in all respects. In particular, to ensure the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational activities" dated May 3, 2019 No. PQ-4307[14], as well as in order to educate young people to become active citizens with a broad outlook on independent life, according to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1059 of December 31, 2019, the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education" was adopted[15]. According to him, effective implementation of the tasks related to the education of the population, especially the youth, provided for in the Action Strategy on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, making them the most necessary basis for a peaceful life providing competencies, developing scientifically based indicators for evaluating spiritual education, relying on the principles of continuity and coherence in the educational process, first of all, proper organization of the mother's pregnancy period, spiritual education of infants and children it is indicated to define the main directions.

Today, the increasing globalization requires a new and systematic approach to education. This is to fully reveal the socio-pedagogical potential of the family, preschool education, general education, secondary special vocational and higher educational institutions, neighborhoods, and high scientific-methodical coherence in the formation of positive qualities in girls. requires a step up. As President Sh. Mirziyoyev noted about this: "Any independent state can achieve high development only if it has a strong moral foundation. For this purpose, we are introducing the subject of "Education" for the first time in general education schools as part of the formation of socially active personal qualities in elementary school girls" [1], it is not without reason that he emphasized. Therefore, the work carried out within this direction is directed towards fulfilling the tasks in the future.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

If girls acquire the qualities of socially active individuals from a young age, they will have their place in society and in the family. In this regard, based on the tasks defined in the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education" in our country, it is necessary to increase the self-confidence and activity of women in the fields of public, politics, law and order, production, education, industry, entrepreneurship, management. . Based on this, we must say that it is necessary to increase the social activity of girls in order to ensure the future of every nation.

F.Abdurahimova[2:158], Z.E.Azimova[3:84], O.Boriev[4:76], N.Dilova[5], among the scientists in our republic on the issues of educating schoolgirls as socially active personalities M. Inomova[6:152], Q.Q. Kuronboyev[8:155], M. Kuronov[9:363], U.Q. Maksudov[10:163], U. Mahkamov[11:32], T. Egamberdiyeva[13:3 -7] and others, who in their research tried to shed light on the pedagogical, social-perceptive aspects of the formation of socially active personal qualities of schoolgirls.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Raising a girl child is a long and continuous gender pedagogical process. In this, the primary school teacher clearly demonstrates his competencies as a pedagogue, coach, and teacher. A primary school teacher should be able to do this work by knowing the personal characteristics of each student, the family pedagogical environment, studying the interests of the students, and skillfully using them as a consistent educational effect. [12:184].

Unity of moral requirements for elementary school students, compatibility of actions, complementing each other, strengthening of achieved spiritual and educational achievements, solving problems together, in harmony, etc. as a result, it is manifested in the social activity of elementary school girls. It is determined that one of the tasks assigned to the head of the elementary school is to establish constant contact with the parents of students, to constantly study their living conditions, family moral environment and to cooperate with them in improving it. Exchanging information about the student's behavior at home, at school, on the street, in the neighborhood, in public places, not only the head of the class, the parents, but also the personality and spirituality of the student. to provide objective information about.

One of the socio-pedagogical tasks of the school is to constantly take care of raising the pedagogical culture of the family, which is its social partner. For this purpose, it is important to organize lectures, discussions, and consultations aimed at increasing the pedagogical knowledge of parents regarding the education of girls. This is done on the initiative of the school in the spiritual and educational cooperation of the school and the family.

Parents, in turn, contribute to the life of the school. In practice, these cooperation activities include holding various meetings, equipping clubs, making visual aids, equipment, organizing excursions, holding conversations, celebrating birthdays, participating in extracurricular educational activities, helping and are helping with advice.

Family and school are the key link in increasing the social activity of elementary school girls. This factor forms complementary components of the overall educational process. That is, the family affects the child through informal, consanguineous ties, and the school as a specialized, special educational institution of the state[7:16].

A primary school teacher should not be indifferent to the interaction, communication, and interaction needs of girls, especially. She should always find time to talk with the class team and each girl. Because girls, especially, always clearly feel the teacher's attitude towards them, react sensitively. They will never share their thoughts and impressions with a teacher

whose job is only to give assignments for daily homework. This harms the effectiveness of spiritual and educational activities conducted in the classroom.

Children should consider a primary school teacher as a close friend, a confidant, a coach who has the same interests as them and can work and live together. Girls are especially sensitive to injustice. Cruelty and injustice towards girls leads to the appearance of negative qualities in their character. Therefore, one of the main conditions for character education in students is the clarity of requirements and confidence in the child's own strength and capabilities. It is especially dangerous for girls to lack confidence in themselves and their own strength, which usually occurs as a result of teachers and mothers saying to a girl that she is "a rag, a slob, she can't do anything." In other words, instilling self-doubt and self-confidence in a girl child is considered the worst pedagogic defect allowed in primary school moral education. The head of the class should be able to find the positive qualities in the girl child and skillfully use them. should be matched.

In Europe and almost all English-speaking countries, the education of girls is mainly based on freedom. They consider it the main factor in economic and social emancipation of girls, as well as finding a place in the family. Especially in the upbringing of girls, their growth with self-confidence is considered as the main issue. Based on these methodological conclusions, to praise the child as the most effective methods in the education of girls - to talk about the child's good sides to himself or to others, to pretend that he is good; advice - speech, advice, admonition, instruction, said in a calm, benevolent situation, in order to guide and educate the child; to comfort - to console a child, his family when something bad happens to him, to comfort him, to stop him from crying, to make him accustomed - to train the standards of manners. For example, to develop and teach the habit of greeting, addressing, showing kindness, etc.; to justify - there are situations when a girl shows excellent behavior and good behavior all year long, and unknowingly makes a mistake. For example, he fights with someone; does not arrive or is late, etc. In such a case, the teacher-class educator must justify him (respecting his previous exemplary behavior); to ask - to get information about the child's scientific and moral knowledge, to check, to conduct an informal examination; demand - persistently asking him for something for the purpose of training; to comfort - to speak and act to comfort and cheer him up if he fails. To describe the examples of positive behavior found in class girls; to emphasize - in every situation spent with girls, to assign moral content that is not comfortable for them; to reward - to appreciate the good behavior of the girl child, evaluate her appropriately, and make her feel that she has value in the team; to prohibit - to forbid something to a girl for educational purposes; to praise - to greet with words like "balli", "well done", to praise and highly evaluate; to equalize - when a girl does something praiseworthy, compare her behavior with the behavior of respectable, dear women, good people, and when she does something bad, compare it with the behavior of women and girls who are called "bad" in fairy tales, books, and movies; to investigate - from time to time to show a sufficient severity to the girl, check, blame her for bad behavior and keep her back from her wrong path; to embarrass - to make a girl feel uncomfortable, embarrassed, embarrassed, embarrassed for her bad behavior; to excite - to convince and please the future by telling about the girl's behavior and success in her studies. To enjoy and please, to satisfy with moral upliftment; to caress - caressing and caressing a girl child as "my dear", "my sister", "my mother"; to beg - to beg, plead with the girl to do or not to do something in order to renew and awaken love in the girl's heart, if there is no other way to blind her;

Reconciliation - to stop the mutual war and conflict that sometimes occurs in the family, in the class, to make an agreement not to fight, to improve the relationship, to reconcile; to play - to play games together with a girl, which are performed according to certain rules and methods, aimed at developing positive qualities and eliminating negative qualities; to teach - to explain and tell the child how to do something (for example, making tea, in public places, in hospitality, to behave in life situations, to speak, etc.) and to do it independently to do; to prevent - if the girl gets angry and decides to do something bad, or if her appearance and behavior show it, to encourage her to refrain from such inappropriate, inappropriate work and behavior; to be interesting - to divert the topic, joke, make the child laugh in order to eliminate the formality and psychological tension in the relationship with the girl; giving gifts - renewing and increasing his love by giving gifts as much as possible on the occasion of holidays and Eids; sponsoring - if a girl is interested in a field (reading, sewing, learning a language) and engages in it, this includes helping, supporting and protecting her in this work.

CONCLUSION

It is necessary to follow the principle of targeted pedagogical influence aimed at ensuring the development of girls in accordance with the goals and ideas of society and their sexual role. Therefore, the methods of education used to educate humanity in girls should be humane and gender specific. For this, it is necessary to learn the qualities of a socially active person in girls, to develop the desire and ability to perform, to organize suitable types of activities, to organize a social pedagogical environment where care for every girl child exists.

In order for the primary school teacher to be able to find the positive qualities in every girl child and use them skillfully, he should skillfully encourage her initiative and will power, help her with his advice and example.

Every qualification and skill that is formed in elementary school girls should be properly taught, constantly repeated and strengthened. This includes: this rule when teaching skills and abilities, showing how girls do skills and abilities, showing gender differences in how boys do them, show them several times first, teach girls how to do them It is necessary to help to fulfill these skills, to constantly reinforce these qualifications and skills, to provide an environment of general cultural, gender behavior, and mutually positive moral and ethical treatment of elementary school girls..

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